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MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF *Dentex maroccanus* IN THE AEGEAN SEA

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Abstract

Dentex maroccanus is one of the least studied species of the family Sparidae. In this work, the relationship of 29 morphometric characters with size was examined, information necessary in stock identification and feeding studies. The relationship of all characters with total length was statistically significant. The linear model fitted the data well, and an increase of each character with length was obvious in all cases.

Key words: *Dentex maroccanus*, morphometrics, Aegean

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1. Introduction

Morocco *Dentex*, *Dentex maroccanus* (Valenciennes, 1830) is a demersal species, member of the family Sparidae. Its distribution extends in the Eastern Atlantic, from the Bay of Biscay to the Gulf of Guinea, the Strait of Gibraltar and the Southern and Eastern Mediterranean (Fisher *et al.* 1987). A few studies on the age, growth, reproduction, fecundity and the spatial distribution of *D. maroccanus* have been conducted in Mediterranean to date (Lamrini & Bouymajjane 2002, Maravelias *et al.* 2007, Mohdeb & Kara 2014, Gul 2014, Taylan *et al.* 2018). Only one published work exists on the species morphology concerning the mean value of 12 morphometric characters (Bayhan *et al.* 2016)

The objective of this work is a preliminary study of the relationship of 29 morphometric characteristics with the total length of the species in the south Aegean Sea. Morphometric measurements are important because they can provide, along with genetics, information on the stock identification of the species and they enhance our knowledge on the species ecology and diet.

2. Materials and methods

Data were reported from samples collected in the South Aegean Sea during September 2014 - May 2015 within the framework of EPILEXIS project. A total of 416 specimens were examined, ranging from 92 to 233 mm Total Length, caught at depths between 68 and 255 m. Fish were frozen immediately after capture. In the laboratory, morphometric measurements to the closest mm using electronic calliper were recorded; these included Total Length, Caudal Peduncle, Pre-anal Length, Snout, Pre-dorsal Length, Dorsal Length, Anal Length, Pectoral Length, Pelvic Length, Body Depth, Caudal Height, Caudal Fin Distance, Body Perimeter, Head Length, Pre-pectoral Length, Post-orbital Length, Eye diameter, Eye height, Inter-orbital Distance, Upper-jaw Length, Lower jaw Length, Head height eye, Head height mid-eye, Lower jaw mouth distance, Between Eyed Width, Mouth Depth, Mouth width, Protrusion upper lip Length and the Eye Lens Size. The relationship for each morphometric character with the TL was studied using the Statgraphics statistical software.

3. Results and Discussion

The relationship between TL and the 29 morphometric characters studied was found to be statistically significant (<0.005) in all cases. Data fitted well linear regression models for all morphometric characters. The slope was also significant in all cases indicating that all morphometric characters increased with increasing TL. Examples of these relationships are given in Figure 1 for the between eyes width (BEW) and the pre-anal length (PrAL) relationships.

Further study to identify differences in these relationships between sex are planned in the future since Byahan *et al.* (2016) found that some morphometric characters are more pronounced for females than males. The relation of some of the above-mentioned morphometric characters with the feeding habits of the species could also be of interest for further studies.

Figure 1. Relationship of the between eyes width (BEW) (left) and the pre-anal length (PrAL) (right) with total length. All measurements in mm.

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References

- Bayhan, B., Heral O., Taskavak E., Topkara E.T., Kara A. (2016) Morphometric characteristics of the Morocco *Dentex Dentex dentex*, Valenciennes, 1830, in the Izmir Bay. Rapp. Comm. Int. Mer Medit. 41. 335.
- Fisher W., Schneider M., Beauchot M.-L. (1987). Fa0 d' Identification des Espèces pour les Besoins de la Pêche. Organisation des Nations Unies pour l'alimentation et l'agriculture, Rome, pp.1529.
- Gul, G. (2014). Age, growth, and reproduction of *Dentex maroccanus* (Actinopterygii: Perciformes: Sparidae) in the Saros Bay (north Aegean Sea). Acta Ichthyologica et Piscatoria 44(4), 295-300.
- Lamrini A., Bouymajjane A. (2002). Biologie de *Dentex maroccanus* (Valenciennes, 1830) dans la région de Safi, in “Actes de l'Av Hassan II.”22(1), Actes Editions, 11-18.
- Maravelias C.D., Tsitsika E.V., Papaconstantinou C. (2007). Evidence of Morocco dentex (*Dentex maroccanus*) distribution in the NE Mediterranean and relationships with environmental factors determined by Generalized Additive Modelling. *Fisheries Oceanography*, 16(3), 294-302.
- Mohdeb R. & Kara M. (2014). Age, growth and reproduction of the Morocco dentex *Dentex maroccanus* of the eastern coast of Algeria. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 95(6), 1261-1270.
- Taylan B., Bayhan B., Heral O. (2018). Fecundity of Morocco Dentex *Dentex maroccanus* Valenciennes, 1830 Distributed in Izmir Bay (Central Aegean Sea of Turkey). *Turkish Journal of Agriculture, Food Science and Technology*,6(5), 624.